

Cyclisation of Acetoacetanilides and Benzoylacetanilides in presence of Polyphosphoric acid

KUSUM DESAI and C. M. DESAI*

P. T. S. College of Science, Surat.

Manuscript received 5 December 1973; revised 29 April 1974; accepted 29 May 1974

Acetoacetanilides, when heated with PPA at lower temperature, have greater tendency to be cyclised to 2-hydroxyquinolines and at higher temperature to 4-hydroxyquinolines; whereas benzoylacetanilides get cyclised mostly to 2-hydroxyquinolines at lower temperature, decomposition taking place at higher temperature; thus temperature is a determining factor in the course of cyclisation. Addition of crotonate or arylamine favours formation of 4-hydroxyquinolines.

PURE acetoacet-2-chloroanilide could not be easily cyclised with polyphosphoric acid to its 2-hydroxy-lepidine, but its mixture with corresponding crotonate or the crude anilide itself could be easily cyclised to its 4-hydroxyquinoline.¹ This transformation is attributed to the ease of the interconvertibility of the anilide into the crotonate and its subsequent cyclisation². Acetoacetanilides on heating with PPA at 140° gave a mixture of 2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxyquinolines and the formation of the latter was explained by the cyclisation of the intermediate anil-anilide formed by the condensation of arylamine, liberated due to the hydrolysis of the anilide, with the unchanged anilide; however, anilides such as acetoacet-2-chloroanilide could not be at all cyclised to 2-hydroxy-lepidines and pyrone-x with a trace of 4-hydroxy isomer was obtained inspite of the fact that acetoacet-2-chloroanilide underwent extensive hydrolysis³.

It may be noted that the 2-hydroxy-lepidine obtained from acetoacet-2-chloroanilide with concentrated sulphuric acid was later on shown to be the 4-hydroxy isomer^{4, 5}.

In the present work it has been found that pure acetoacet-2-chloroanilide could be cyclised with PPA to (i) 4-hydroxyquinoline at higher temperature or (ii) a mixture of 2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxy isomer or (iii) 2-hydroxy isomer under specific conditions at lower temperatures; even the crude anilide under such conditions gave with PPA a mixture of 2-hydroxy and 4-hydroxy isomers, having at higher temperature greater tendency for cyclisation to 4-hydroxyquinolines, whereas at lower temperature greater tendency for 2-hydroxy isomers.

Pure acetoacet-4-methylanilide, which gave at 140° with PPA only 2-hydroxy isomer, was found, when mixed with *p*-toluidine, to give a mixture of 2-isomer (45%) and 4-isomer (26%)³. In this work, the crude anilide, which gave at a lower temperature a mixture of 2-isomer (52%) and 4-isomer (21%), gave, when mixed with *p*-toluidine, a mixture of 2-isomer (7.5%) and 4-isomer (67%). Thus the presence of free arylamine or the crotonate¹ influences the course of cyclisation towards the 4-isomer. However, such an influence was not observed in the case of the corresponding benzoylacetanilide.

Pure benzoylacetanilides gave with PPA at 140°-150° a mixture of the corresponding 4-hydroxy isomers (20%), and a small amount of the 2-hydroxy isomers or only 2-hydroxy isomers (low yields) depending on the less or more proportion of PPA⁶, some of the anilides being decomposed. In the present work crude benzoylacetanilides gave with PPA very high yields of the corresponding 2-hydroxyquinolines (75 to 80%) with negligible amount of 4-isomers by heating the reaction mixture at lower temperature (60° to 90°), keeping it overnight and then heating at higher temperature 140°-150°. The anilides, such as benzoylacet-*p*-nitroanilide, found to undergo decomposition in the earlier work⁶, gave lower yields (20 to 42%).

Further, the higher proportion of phosphoric anhydride in PPA was found to favour the formation of the 2-hydroxy isomer in case of benzoylacet-*p*-toluidide; whereas the less favoured at high temperature the formation of the 4-isomer. Addition of free *p*-toluidine to the anilide did not favour the formation of the 4-isomer as in the case of acetoacet-*p*-toluidide. The formation of 4-hydroxyquinolines from benzoylacetanilides was explained due to Fries type rearrangement⁶ giving *o*-aminobenzoyl ketone being cyclised to the 4-hydroxyquinoline.

The mechanism operating in the course of cyclisation of the anilides in presence of PPA from 2-hydroxy to 4-hydroxyquinolines depends on (i) the presence of the crotonate² or (ii) the presence of the arylamine due to hydrolysis³ or (iii) a Fries type rearrangement⁶. The former two are possible in case of acetoacetanilides, while the third is possible with benzoylacetanilides. These conclusions are explained as follows:

The participation of the acetyl group of acetoacetanilides in the mechanism (i) or (ii) is easier due to its greater reactivity as compared to that of the benzoyl group of benzoylacetanilides; because the phenyl group attached to the carbonyl group, reduces its activity because of its delocalized π orbitals acting as powerful electron source; the carbonyl group of benzoylacetanilide does not enter into anil-anilide formation with arylamine. Fries type rearrangement giving *o*-aminobenzoylacetophenone followed by ring-closure would lead to 4-hydroxyquinoline. Such a rearrangement has been found to take place with simple anilides, such as benzanilides⁷.

Experimental

8-Chloro-4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline (I) and 8-chloro-2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinoline (II) :

Pure acetoacet-2-chloroanilide (III, 1.8 g), mixed with PPA (20 g P_2O_5 : 12 ml H_3PO_4) at 65° , kept overnight, was heated at $65-70^\circ$ for 5hr; after keeping the mass overnight it was heated at 95° for 1 hr and then at 140° . Neutralisation gave the product which was fractionally crystallised from aqueous alcohol. The less soluble (I) fraction (0.81 g, m.p. 212°) did not give ferric chloride coloration; dichloroderivative, m.p. $105^\circ-106^\circ$. The second fraction (II, 0.83 g; m.p. 230°) gave purple coloration; dichloroderivative, m.p. $86^\circ-87^\circ$.

PPA with pentoxide (28 g) gave higher yield of (I)-1.03 g.

The mixture of (III, 3 g) with PPA was heated at $70^\circ-80^\circ$ for 1 hr, kept for 48 hr and heated to $140^\circ-150^\circ$. The product (II, 1.4 g) was crystallised from water, m.p. 230° .

The mixtures of pure (III, 2.5g) and the corresponding crotonate (0.5 to 1g) gave with PPA only (II) after treatment with PPA at 140° for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hr.

The crude anilides, obtained by refluxing for few minutes, arylamine and ethylacetoacetate (0.025 mole each) were cyclised as follows :

Method (a) : The crude anilide, mixed with PPA at $5^\circ-10^\circ$ and kept overnight, was heated at 65° for 3 hr and finally at $140^\circ-150^\circ$. After neutralisation 2- and 4-isomers were separated by alkali treatment and crystallised from aqueous alcohol; mixed m.p.s showed no depression.

Method (b) : The mixture of anilide with PPA at 100° was heated at $140^\circ-150^\circ$ for 1-2 hr. Isomers were separated by alkali treatment.

Details for other anilides are given in the Table 1.

Cyclisation of crude benzoylacetanilides :

PPA : Pentoxide (20 g) was dissolved into phosphoric acid (12 ml) by heating at 95° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr; more pentoxide (8 g) was added and the mass again heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Undissolved scum being removed.

Cyclisation : The crude anilide, obtained by refluxing arylamine and ethyl benzoylacetate (0.025 mole each), mixed with PPA at $65^\circ-70^\circ$, was heated to 95° giving effervescence. The mass was kept overnight and heated further at $100^\circ-110^\circ$ for 1 hr and finally at $140^\circ-150^\circ$ for 1 hr. The alkali insoluble 2-hydroxyquinoline was crystallised from aqueous alcohol. Mixed m.p.s showed no depression.

4-Phenyl-2-hydroxy-6-nitroquinoline

The crude anilide, prepared from *p*-nitroaniline (2.0 g) and the β -ketoester (3.5 g), was treated with PPA as above. The alkali insoluble product was washed with dilute acetic acid. It was crystallised from alcohol (charcoal), when yellow powder (m. p. 296° , 0.67 g) was obtained. π (Analysis : Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}N_2O_3$; N, 10.52; Found : N, 10.43).

On refluxing with a mixture of phosphorous oxychloride and pentachloride, it gave 4-phenyl-2-chloro-6-nitroquinoline; yellow needles, m.p. $135^\circ-136^\circ$.

(Analysis : Calc. for $C_{15}H_9N_2O_2Cl$; N, 9.84; Found : N, 9.81).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the college authority for providing facilities for research work.

TABLE I

CYCLISATION OF $ARNHCO.CH_2-CO.CH_3$ & $-CO.C_6H_5$

Ar (1)	Cyclisation reagent PPA and method (2)	Product hydroxyquinoline (3)	Yield (%) (4)	M.P. $^\circ C$ (5)
2- CH_3 - C_6H_4	(a)	4, 8-Dimethyl-2-	69	217
"	(b)	2, 8-Dimethyl-4-	58	263
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	(a)	4, 8-Dimethyl-2-	3	217
"	(b)	4, 6-Dimethyl-2-	52	245
"	(b)	2, 6-Dimethyl-4-	21	278
"	(b)	2, 6-Dimethyl-4-	69	278
"	(b)	4, 6-Dimethyl-2-	3	245
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	(a)	2, 6-Dimethyl-4-	67	278
+ P- CH_3 - C_6H_4 . NH_2 (0.0125 M)	PPA(18 g:30 ml)-(a)	4, 6-Dimethyl-2-	7.5	245
" + "		2, 6-Dimethyl-4-	77.5	278
" + "		4, 6-Dimethyl-2-	9.5	245
2-Cl- C_6H_4	(a)	2-methyl-8-Cl-4-	26	230
"	(a)	4-methyl-8-Cl-2-	12	212
C_6H_5	Cyclising agent PPA	4-phenyl-2-hydroxyquinoline	75.7	256
2- CH_3 - C_6H_4	"	8-methyl-	77.5	217
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	"	6-	80	243
2, 4-(CH_3) ₂ - C_6H_3	"	6, 8-dimethyl-	81.7	250
4-O CH_3 - C_6H_4	"	6-methoxy-	42.4	241
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4 + <i>p</i> -toluidine (0.0125 M)	"	6-methyl-	79.5	242-243
4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	(16 g:16 ml)	6-methyl-	25	243
	at $140^\circ-150^\circ$	& 6-methyl-4-hydroxy Isomer	35.5	296

KUSUM DESAI & C. M. DESAI : CYCLISATION OF ACETOACETANILIDES & BENZOYLACETANILIDES

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